

A model using an inter-sectorial data integration process indicates that reducing *Campylobacter* cross-contamination at slaughter mitigates the risk of human campylobacteriosis effectively

Alessandro Foddai^{a,*}, Maarten Nauta^b, Johanne Ellis-Iversen^c

^a National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, Research Group for Foodborne Pathogens and Epidemiology, Kgs. Lyngby, 2800, Denmark

^b Department for Infectious Disease Epidemiology and Prevention, Statens Serum Institute, Copenhagen 2300, Denmark

^c Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, Glostrup 2600, Denmark

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ABSTRACT

The risk of human campylobacteriosis due to Danish broiler flocks cross-contaminated (CC) at slaughter with *Campylobacter* spp. was assessed. National surveillance data (2018) on flock *Campylobacter* status (called animal level component (AL)) and on contamination of chilled carcasses ready for consumption (food safety component (FS)), were compared. The AL component consisted of PCR testing results on pools of cloacal swabs collected from 3,012 conventional flocks, while the FS component presented culture testing of leg skins from 999 (of the 3,012) randomly sampled flocks. Datasets were integrated on flocks tested in both components, by combinations of farm-ID, house-unit and sampling date. The CC flocks were those entering the slaughterhouse as AL-negative, but resulting FS-positive. All remaining carcass positive flocks were instead classified as *Non-CC* flocks. The apparent prevalence (AP) of carcass positive flocks and the colony forming units per gram (cfu/g), measured by the FS component, were fed into a published simulation model, to assess under three simulation scenarios: the mean monthly risk per serving during 2018, relative (RR) to that of 2013 (reference year in the current Danish Action Plan). In the baseline scenario, the original AL status and the FS cfu/g were maintained. In the alternative scenarios I and II, the FS cfu/g were set = 0 (i.e. negative) for the *Non-CC* and for the *CC* flocks, respectively. Thus, scenario I and the differences between the other two scenarios, provided the contribution of the *CC* flocks to the AP and to the RR. The (overall) annual median log₁₀ cfu/g was ≈ 2.8 (min. = 1.0; max. = 4.0) for the *Non-CC* flocks and 1.4 (1.0; 3.9) for the *CC* flocks. The median monthly difference in AP, between the baseline scenario and scenario II was 7% (min = 2% in January; max = 19% in August), while the difference in risk was 0.04% (0.001%; 0.11%), which was similar to the mean monthly risk under scenario I. If cross-contamination had not occurred (scenario II), the annual AP would have reduced from 24.3% to 16.1% and the RR would have reduced from 0.92 to 0.77. Therefore, ≈16% of the public health risk posed by Danish conventional broiler meat, appeared attributable to *CC* flocks. Reducing cross-contamination could mitigate the risk of human campylobacteriosis notably. This study illustrates how inter-sectorial surveillance data integration, can be used to optimize National Action Plans against *Campylobacter* spp. and other similar foodborne pathogens.

1. Introduction

Campylobacter spp. is the most common cause of bacterial gastroenteritis in humans and contaminated poultry meat is considered to be the most frequent food source of disease (campylobacteriosis) (EFSA and ECDC, 2016; Hansson et al., 2018; WHO, 2020).

In the EU, risk mitigation measures aimed to reduce meat contamination and the burden of disease, are usually prioritized at farm level

(EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011, 2020). Cross-contamination from positive flocks to negative flocks, can occur during: transport, slaughter, and/or meat processing (Allen et al., 2007; Berndtson et al., 1996; Miwa et al., 2003; Rasschaert et al., 2020). However, most often, cross-contaminated (*CC*) flocks have less *Campylobacter* than flocks, which arrive positive at the slaughterhouse (Allen et al., 2007; Johannessen et al., 2007; Elvers et al., 2011; Seliwiorstow et al., 2016; Foddai et al., 2022b). Therefore, it is generally assumed that, flocks cross-contaminations do not pose a

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: alefo@food.dtu.dk (A. Foddai).

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“relevant risk” of disease for humans. In evaluating control strategies, previously (independently) developed food chain risk assessments, from different countries, found a negligible-very low effect of logistic slaughter (processing of “expected” negative flocks before “expected” positive flocks) (Rosenquist et al., 2003; Nauta et al., 2009; EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011). However, others suggested that the application of logistic slaughter and/or the definition of critical control points at the slaughterhouse (Food Safety Commission of Japan, 2009; Sasaki et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2018; Dogan et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2020), could reduce cross-contamination and the risk for humans notably. Therefore, further evaluations of the impact of CC flocks on human health are needed, especially if those can be based on the integration of national surveillance datasets, which allow identifying CC flocks with good precision.

In Denmark, the National Action Plan against *Campylobacter* is informed through surveillance data collected at different levels of the food chain, “from chicken farm to human patients” (Gantzhorn et al., 2018; Houe et al., 2019; Kuhn et al., 2020). One surveillance component, which is based on testing of cloacal swabs from all slaughtered broiler flocks, provides information about the farm/animal infection status. Another surveillance component, based on random testing of leg skin samples collected from chilled carcasses, monitors the level of contamination at the end of the slaughter line, where the meat is ready for human consumption. Those components are here referred as: animal level (AL) and food safety (FS) components, in line with a previous study (Foddai et al., 2022b), where the same data was used to assess the frequency and the level of cross-contamination in Danish slaughterhouses. A third surveillance stream gathers data on human campylobacteriosis from the clinical microbiological laboratories, when notified to the public health authorities, through the national microbiological database.

Moreover, within the National Action Plan, a simulation model (Teunis and Havelaar, 2000; Nauta et al., 2008, 2012; Foddai et al., 2022a) is used since 2014, to assess the risk of campylobacteriosis per serving prepared with fresh broiler meat produced in Denmark, during each year. This risk is also measured as relative (RR) compared to the estimate from 2013 (year of reference) (Gantzhorn et al., 2018; Anonymous, 2019). The risk model is informed with the apparent prevalence (AP) of carcass positive flocks (which means that the prevalence is not corrected for test performance), and with the concentration (cfu/g) of *Campylobacter* spp. measured by the FS component (Foddai et al., 2022a, 2022b).

The overall goals and implementation of the Action Plan are revised and updated each 3–4 years. Within this context, two Danish studies were previously carried out. Foddai et al., 2022a found that, if farms classified at higher risk of infection from the AL testing of 2018, had delivered only carcass negative flocks during the following year, the RR of 2019 would have reduced from 0.94 to 0.51. In Foddai et al., 2022b, it was assessed that during 2018, approximately 8–9% of the flocks, which arrived as cloacal negative at the slaughterhouse, were then positive on the carcasses, and thus, were likely to have been cross-contaminated during slaughter. Those CC flocks had a concentration of *Campylobacter* (cfu/g), which was significantly lower than that of flocks classified as positive in both surveillance components. Consequently, within the Action Plan, it was decided to investigate the relative contribution of the CC flocks on the overall risk per serving and to the RR. Therefore, the aim of this study was to quantitatively assess the impact of the CC flocks identified through the surveillance data integration carried out in Foddai et al. (2022b), on the risk of human campylobacteriosis posed by a meal prepared with fresh poultry meat originated from Danish conventional broiler flocks.

2. Materials and methods

The data, the risk assessment model and procedures used in this study, are similar to these applied in Foddai et al. (2022a). The main

difference is that here, we assessed the impact of the CC flocks identified from data 2018 (Foddai et al., 2022b), on the risk of human campylobacteriosis during the same year. Whereas in Foddai et al. (2022a), as explained above, the risk assessment was carried out for 2019, considering the flocks delivered by farms classified at higher risk of infection, through the cloacal swabs testing of the previous year. In the sections below is provided a short review of the data and of the model. We refer to the previous studies (Foddai et al., 2022a; 2022b), if more detailed information is needed.

2.1. The national surveillance data

In this study, a flock was defined as the group of broilers grown in the same house unit on the same farm and slaughtered on the same day. The data integration and the descriptive statistics on flock contamination level and prevalence, were carried out using the software R (R Core Team, 2013).

Data from the AL component regarded 3012 conventional flocks tested in pools of cloacal swabs, with a polymerase chain reaction (PCR) (Lund et al., 2004). From each slaughtered flock a pool of 12 swabs (one swab per pair of randomly selected broilers) was tested and results were reported as positive or negative. This component tested all conventional broiler flocks slaughtered at the two major Danish slaughterhouses (called S1 and S2 here), which process most (>90%) of the conventional flocks produced in the country (Gantzhorn et al., 2018). A third slaughterhouse (S3) exports most of the meat and during the year of reference (2013) was not opened yet. Therefore, data from that company was not considered within the National Action Plan, when the risk of campylobacteriosis per serving was assessed for the Danish human population. Accordingly, surveillance data from this third slaughterhouse was not used in this study either (Foddai et al., 2022a; 2022b).

Data from the FS component contained randomized testing of approximately one third (999/3012) of all flocks slaughtered at S1 and S2. In this component, each selected flock was classified by using a *Campylobacter* culture test (Nordic Committee on Food Analysis, 2007; Rosenquist et al., 2007) on a single leg skin sample per flock. Results were reported as cfu/g. Legs (i.e. flocks) with ≥ 10 cfu/g of *Campylobacter* were classified as carcass positive and otherwise as negative (Foddai et al., 2022b). Accordingly, samples with less than 10 cfu/g were reported as = 0 (i.e. considered negative) in the data and in the risk assessment model (next Section).

In Foddai et al. (2022b), the CC flocks were identified by integrating data from the two surveillance components (AL and FS) in different ways. For instance, when considering only flocks registered across both components with (exactly) the same farm-ID (Central Husbandry Register or CHR number), house unit and sampling date; then 283 out of the 999 flocks tested in both components could be compared on the flock status classification (positive or negative) and contamination. Instead, when a date discrepancy of up to 4–7 days was allowed between datasets, the flock status could be compared across components for 949 of the 999 flocks. Nevertheless, the percentage of flocks classified as cross-contaminated was similar (8.1% vs. 8.6%) in the two data handling methods. For this study, the (latter) highest matching frequency between components was used (Table, 1), because it was considered more representative.

It should be noted that, in Foddai et al. (2022b), the contaminations of the 82 CC flocks were statistically compared against these of the 152 Non-CC flocks (Table, 1 PosBoth), which were positive in both components, and at the same time, could be matched between datasets. In this study, we additionally considered the 9 FS positive flocks and the 41 FS negative flocks, which could not be matched between datasets in Foddai et al. (2022b) (e.g. due to typing errors in the data); because all carcass positive flocks (matched and not) contributed to the annual baseline risk assessment of the Danish Action Plan. Accordingly, 243 of the 999 flocks tested in both components were carcass positive: the 234 flocks from Table 1, plus 9 FS positive flocks unmatched between datasets. Between

Table 1

Classification (from Foddai et al., 2022b) for 949 of the 999 broiler flocks (2018), which were tested from S1-S2 and could be matched across surveillance datasets of the animal level (AL) and the food safety (FS) components. Testing results obtained on the same flock as (+) = positive or (-) = negative, were matched across datasets, by combinations of: farm-ID (Central Husbandry Register or CHR number), house unit and sampling date (maximum discrepancy of $\pm 4-7$ days, between the two dates).

<i>Campylobacter</i> status	AL (+)	AL (-)	Total
FS (+)	PosBoth = 152 (16.0%)	CC = 82 (8.6%)	234 (24.7%)
FS (-)	ALonlyPos = 14 (1.5%)	NegBoth = 701 (73.9%)	715 (75.3%)
Total	166 (17.5%)	783 (82.5%)	949 (100.0%)

PosBoth = Matched flocks classified as positive in both components; NegBoth = Matched flocks classified as negative in both components; ALonlyPos = Matched flocks classified as positive only in the AL component and CC = Matched flocks classified as positive only in the FS component (cross-contaminated flocks).

those, 82 flocks were still classified as CC (Table 1) and 161 as carcass positive but *Non-CC* flocks. The remaining unmatched 41 flocks were carcass-negative, and thus were fed into the model with cfu/g = 0 for all simulation scenarios.

2.2. The risk assessment model

The applied risk assessment model, relates the probability of human campylobacteriosis caused by consumption of a meal-serving prepared with fresh broiler meat in a month/year, to the concentration detected on the leg skins at the FS component. It combines a consumer phase model, which describes the transfer and survival of *Campylobacter* during food preparation and the subsequent exposure to the consumer (Nauta et al., 2008), with a dose response model (Teunis and Havelaar, 2000), as explained in Section 2.2, eqs. (1)–(7) of the paper by Nauta et al. (2012).

Therefore, the first output of the model was the risk per serving depending on month (or monthly risk per serving). Next, the annual level RR was calculated by dividing the mean monthly risk per serving estimated across the 12 months of 2018; by the mean monthly risk per serving estimated across the 12 months of 2013. Therefore, for both years, the risk per serving was calculated by feeding the monthly surveillance data into the model, i.e. the monthly AP of positive leg skin samples and the respective concentrations of *Campylobacter* (i.e. the cfu/g). Accordingly, the AP represented a simplified-combined probability that the poultry meat used for human consumption arrived from a broiler carrying ≥ 10 cfu/g and that such a broiler belonged to a flock with contaminated carcasses, because infected from the farm (*Non-CC* flock) or because cross-contaminated (*CC* flock) at slaughter. The concentrations were fed into the model as reported in the FS dataset. Therefore, flocks classified as culture negative (<10 cfu/g) were entered with 0 cfu/g, while the culture positive flocks were entered with the original cfu/g reported from the laboratory (≥ 10), which were log₁₀ transformed in the model.

An annual RR = 1 would suggest no change in the mean monthly risk compared to the year of reference, while RR > 1 or RR < 1, would suggest a decrease or an increase of the mean monthly risk per serving, respectively.

2.3. Relating the surveillance information on CC flocks with the risk of disease

To assess quantitatively the impact of cross-contamination on the risk of human campylobacteriosis, the information obtained from the two surveillance components had to be integrated and fed into the risk

assessment model. For that purpose, three steps were followed:

- Firstly, the distribution of *Campylobacter*'s concentrations was compared between the *CC* and the *Non-CC* flocks. In Foddai et al. (2022b), this comparison was carried out considering all (annual) leg skin results together and through a statistical analysis. Here, contamination distributions across monthly surveillance periods were graphically illustrated to show effects of seasonality on the different carcass contamination levels between flock types (*CC* vs. *Non-CC*); and to understand how such contaminations related with the monthly risk per serving.
- Secondly, the AP measured through the FS component in Foddai et al. (2022b), represented a baseline percentage of carcass contaminated flocks, at the end of the slaughter line (on broiler meat ready for consumption). Thereafter, the AP was re-estimated assigning cfu/g = 0 to all *CC* flocks (i.e. setting all *CC* flocks as carcass negative, see scenario II below). The difference between the two AP values represented the impact of cross-contamination on the monthly measured prevalence of flocks positive at the culture test.
- Finally, the risk assessment model was used to investigate, under three simulation scenarios, the combined impact of the meat contamination levels and of the AP, on the risk of human campylobacteriosis. For that purpose, the risk per serving was firstly assessed under the baseline scenario, where all carcass positive flocks (*CC* and *Non-CC*) were kept with their original concentrations observed through the FS component. Outputs of the baseline scenario were then compared with those of two alternative scenarios: I and II. In scenario I, the concentrations were set to 0 cfu/g for all *Non-CC* flocks, whereas in scenario II this change was applied only to the *CC* flocks.

Therefore, through the three scenarios, the risk per serving posed by any kind of carcass positive flock (baseline scenario), or by the *CC* flocks (scenario I), or by the *Non-CC* flocks (scenario II) were assessed. Furthermore, by comparing the annual level RR of the baseline scenario vs. that of scenario II, it was investigated the potential impact of the Action Plan on the risk per serving, if carcass positivity due to between-flocks cross-contamination could be completely removed.

3. Results

3.1. Comparison of meat contamination levels between CC and non-CC flocks

In the *Non-CC* flocks, the (overall) annual median log₁₀ cfu/g was ≈ 2.8 (min. = 1.0; max. = 4.0). While it was ≈ 1.4 (min. = 1.0; max. = 3.9) in the *CC* flocks (Fig. 1a).

For the *Non-CC* flocks, the monthly median log₁₀ cfu/g ranged from 2.4 in May to 3.3 in April. While for the *CC* flocks, it ranged from 1.0 in April to 2.5 in June (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1b shows in which months and in which kind of flocks (*CC* vs. *Non-CC*), a "higher than usual" level of carcass contamination occurred. If a critical concentration of 1000 cfu/g (i.e. 3.0 log₁₀ cfu/g) (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel 2011; Nauta et al., 2012) was applied as a maximum tolerated limit of meat contamination (violet horizontal line), then part of the *Non-CC* flocks exceeded this limit in March, April, June to October and December. Whereas the *CC* flocks exceeded such a limit only in March and June.

3.2. Impact of cross-contamination on flock prevalence measured by carcass testing

The monthly number of FS tested flocks, with the respective number of *CC* and *Non-CC* flocks, are shown in Fig. 2. In 10 out of 12 months, the number of *Non-CC* flocks was higher than the number of *CC* flocks. The only exceptions occurred in May and November, when 6 flocks were

Fig. 1. A comparison of annual log₁₀ transformed distributions of colony forming units per gram (cfu/g) between *Campylobacter* carcass positive flocks (2018) classified as cross-contaminated (CC, green boxplot) or carcass positive but not cross-contaminated (Non-CC flocks, red boxplot). The CC flocks were those that arrived at the slaughterhouse as negative in cloacal swabs (i.e. at the Animal Level or AL component), but resulted positive in legs skins (Food Safety or FS component). While the Non-CC flocks were those that were positive in both surveillance streams (152 flocks), or were positive on carcasses, but could not be classified as CC flocks because merging between components could not be achieved (9 flocks). YES = cross-contaminated. NO = not cross-contaminated. Fig. 1b Comparison of monthly log₁₀ transformed distributions of colony forming units per gram (cfu/g) between *Campylobacter* carcass positive flocks (2018) classified as cross-contaminated (CC, green boxplots) or carcass positive but not cross-contaminated (Non-CC flocks, red boxplots). The CC flocks were those that arrived at the slaughterhouse as negative in cloacal swabs (i.e. at the Animal Level or AL component), but resulted positive in legs skins (Food Safety or FS component). While the Non-CC flocks were those that were positive in both surveillance streams (152 flocks), or were positive on carcasses, but could not be classified as CC flocks because merging between components could not be achieved (9 flocks). The violet horizontal line represents a potential threshold in meat contamination, if a critical limit of 1000 cfu/g (i.e. 3.0 log₁₀ cfu/g) (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel 2011; Nauta et al., 2012) was applied as a maximum tolerated level of meat contamination.

represents a potential threshold in meat contamination, if a critical limit of 1000 cfu/g (i.e. 3.0 log₁₀ cfu/g) (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel 2011; Nauta et al., 2012) was applied as a maximum tolerated level of meat contamination.

Fig. 2. Monthly number of *Campylobacter* carcass tested (Total LS tested) and positive (Total LS (+)) flocks during 2018 (from Foddai et al., 2022b), with the respective number of flocks classified as cross-contaminated (LS (+) cross-contaminated) or not cross-contaminated (LS (+) non cross-contaminated). The CC flocks were those that arrived at the slaughterhouse as negative in cloacal swabs (i.e. at the Animal Level or AL component), but resulted positive in legs skins (LS, Food Safety or FS component). While the Non-CC flocks were those that were positive in both surveillance streams (152 flocks), or were positive on carcasses, but could not be classified as CC flocks because merging between components could not be achieved (9 flocks).

classified as CC and 2 or 1 (respectively), were classified as *Non-CC*.

The monthly median number of *Non-CC* flocks was 8 and ranged from 1 (in November) to 36 flocks (in August). Whereas the monthly median number of *CC* flocks was 6 and ranged from 2 (in January, February and December) to 17 flocks (in August).

In the baseline scenario, the annual AP was $243/999 = 24.3\%$ (Foddai et al., 2022b), while it was $(243-82)/999 = 16.1\%$ in scenario II (where the *CC* flocks were set with $\text{cfu/g} = 0 = \text{FS negative}$). Thus, the *CC* flocks contributed to one third of the annual AP of carcass positive flocks detected through the FS component.

The median monthly difference between the two AP estimates (i.e. the monthly *CC* prevalence) was 7% (min = 2% in January; max = 19% in August) (Fig. 3).

As shown in Foddai et al. (2022b), the impact of *CC* flocks on the national prevalence of carcass positive flocks, was higher during summer months than during the rest of the year (Fig. 3). Thus, cross-contamination was more likely to occur between June and September, as previously reported (Foddai et al., 2022b).

3.3. Impact of cross-contamination on the risk of human campylobacteriosis

The monthly risk per serving is shown in Fig. 4, for each simulated scenario. The median monthly difference in risk between the baseline scenario and scenario II (i.e. removing carcass positivity due to cross-contamination), was 0.04% (min = 0.001% in January; max = 0.11% in August), and was similar to the risk simulated in scenario I (Fig. 4, green bar). The contribution of the *CC* flocks to the overall monthly risk per serving was higher during summer, when the AP of carcass positive flocks (Figs. 2 and 3) increased.

Across the 12 months of 2018, the mean monthly risk per serving was 0.25% (median 0.20%) under the baseline scenario, while it was 0.04% (median 0.03%) in scenario I and 0.21% (median 0.16%) in scenario II.

The annual level RR, would have reduced from 0.92 (baseline scenario) to 0.77 (scenario II), i.e. of $(0.92-0.77)/0.92 = 16.3\%$, if flock cross-contamination, had not occurred at all in 2018.

4. Discussion

In this study, we investigated the impact of between-flocks cross-contamination, during transport and/or the slaughter process on: (i) the

monthly meat contamination levels, (ii) the monthly apparent prevalence of carcass positive flocks, and (iii) the risk of human campylobacteriosis per serving. It was estimated that $\approx 16\%$ of the public health risk associated with the consumption of a broiler meat meal, is attributable to carcasses obtained from cross-contaminated flocks. Therefore, if the simulated “hypothetical” scenario II (without cross-contaminations) was achieved, we would expect that the average risk per serving would reduce by $\approx 16\%$ in future years of the Action Plan (e.g. 2023–2026). This estimated relative contribution of the *CC* flocks to the overall risk, is much more than expected on the basis of other quantitative microbiological risk assessments models for broiler processing (Nauta et al., 2009). It implies that control measures to prevent cross-contamination may be more effective than previously thought (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011) and that the cross-contamination between broiler flocks requires more research, to understand the underlying dynamics.

To our knowledge, this is the first study, where the risk of campylobacteriosis due to *CC* flocks, is assessed using surveillance data, which is systematically collected from farms and slaughterhouses, through surveillance components of the same country and year. The applied data integration procedure and the results obtained, can help the risk communication between surveillance actors and stakeholders, and can create a common understanding of the relative importance for public health of cross-contamination between broiler flocks. In this way, the National Action Plans could be continuously improved, because (eventual) actions of disease control can be justified and prioritized along the food chain (from farm to fork), so that their “acceptability” (Bogaardt et al., 2004) can be optimized between the surveillance actors and stakeholders.

Understanding from, as well as engagement of surveillance actors and stakeholders, are essential when National Action Plans aim to succeed as “One Health” systems. This is particularly true for diseases like campylobacteriosis, for which the control is a priority for the public health sector, but it would not necessarily be for the animal (pre-harvest level) and for the food safety sectors (post-harvest level). In fact, *Campylobacter* rarely-unlikely causes production losses in infected broiler farms and does not alter the organoleptic quality of contaminated carcasses. However, the farmers, the meat processing industry, and/or governments could be facing most of the costs for control actions (Mangen et al., 2005; Havelaar et al., 2007) to optimize food safety for humans. Hence, to achieve the aimed targets of National Action Plans

Fig. 3. Monthly apparent prevalence (AP) of *Campylobacter* carcass positive flocks during 2018 (from Foddai et al. (2022b)), according to the baseline scenario (original AP) and to the alternative scenario II (red line) where cross-contaminated (*CC*) flocks were set as carcass negative with meat concentration = 0 cfu/g . The *CC* flocks were those that arrived at the slaughterhouse as negative in cloacal swabs (i.e. at the Animal Level or AL component), but resulted positive in legs skins (Food Safety or FS component). While the *Non-CC* flocks were those that were positive in both surveillance streams (152 flocks), or were positive on carcasses but could not be classified as *CC* flocks, because merging between components could not be achieved (9 flocks). The difference between the two lines represents the impact of *CC* flocks on the monthly AP. The line for scenario I ($\text{cfu/g} = 0$ for all *Non-CC* flocks) is not shown because it would correspond to the difference between the black and the red line.

Fig. 4. Risk of human campylobacteriosis per serving depending on month, due to consumption of a meal prepared with chicken meat produced in Denmark during 2018. Black bars represent the monthly risk according to the baseline scenario, which was informed with the original apparent prevalence (AP) of carcass positive flocks and the concentrations measured through leg skin testing (FS component). In the alternative scenario I (green bars), all not cross-contaminated (Non-CC) flocks were set with $\text{cfu/g} = 0$, while in scenario II (red bars), all cross-contaminated (CC) flocks had $\text{cfu/g} = 0$. The CC flocks were those that arrived at the slaughterhouse as negative in cloacal swabs (i.e. at the Animal Level or AL component), but resulted positive in legs skins (Food Safety or FS component). While the Non-CC flocks were those that were positive in both surveillance streams (152 flocks), or were positive on carcasses, but could not be classified as CC flocks because merging between components could not be achieved (9 flocks).

against *Campylobacter* spp. (as well as against other similar foodborne zoonosis), it is preferable that the impact of control measures is evaluated as objectively as possible and is properly communicated along the food chain, to those who should face the pathogen's control efforts.

4.1. Interpretation of outputs to optimize risk-based control measures along the food chain

When looking at the monthly risk per serving estimates provided in Fig. 4, it could be tempting to multiply their average by the number of residents present in Denmark, to estimate the annual incidence of cases that could be expected in the country; and to compare such an estimate with the incidence reported in the country during the same year. However, such a comparison is challenging, because the specific proportion of human campylobacteriosis cases attributable to Danish broiler meat produced by S1 and S2 is unknown, and there is considerable uncertainty when comparing simulated number of cases versus incidence data (Boysen et al., 2013; Evers and Bouwknegt, 2016; Havelaar et al., 2013; Pires et al., 2020). On one hand the uncertainty attending especially the dose response model is large (Bouwknegt et al., 2014). On the other hand, the number of reported cases eventually used to validate the model's estimates, should be corrected for factors of underreporting and underdiagnosis, which are difficult to define and can vary remarkably between studies (Havelaar et al., 2013; Pires et al., 2020).

For that reason, within the Danish Action Plan, not only the flock prevalence (AP) (Figs. 2 and 3), the cfu/g (Fig. 1a,b) and the monthly risk estimates (Fig. 4) are considered, to monitor the impact of the control measures across years; but the RR value is mainly used as final output of reference. The latter gives a quantitative estimate of the change in risk per serving, during a specific year of the Action Plan, relative to the year of reference (2013). In the RR, similar uncertainties present in the two mean monthly risk estimates that are divided, partly cancel out (Nauta et al., 2009; Christensen et al., 2013) between years. Thus, changes in the RR predominantly represent changes in risk per serving, which are caused by the actual changes of the AP and cfu/g observed from the data (i.e. epidemiological changes).

For years 2018–2021, the National Action Plan was aimed to reduce the RR by 50% (Anonymous, 2019). In Foddai et al. (2022a) it was assessed that such a target could be approached if the flocks delivered by farms classified at high risk (with > 5 AL positive flocks per year), had been always negative. Whereas in this study, we estimated that if cross-contamination could be avoided, the RR would reduce of $\approx 16\%$. When considering the two risk-assessment outputs altogether, it can be decided what kind of risk mitigation actions to prioritize or optimize, along the poultry meat chain.

Control measures targeted at farm level (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011, 2020; Foddai et al., 2022a), and especially at high-risk farms, could have the direct effect of reducing the prevalence of highly contaminated flocks (the Non-CC flocks here) entering the slaughterhouse; but also the indirect effect of reducing cross-contamination during processing, from positives towards originally negative flocks. Meanwhile, cross-contamination and its related risk could be reduced: by enhancing of slaughterline operations, through the identification of slaughterhouses critical control points, by using specific treatment/s (e.g. freezing), and/or through logistic slaughter (Rosenquist et al., 2006; Osiriphun et al., 2011; EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011; Habib et al., 2012; Hansson et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2020). Therefore, risk mitigation at the farm and at the slaughterhouse, should not be considered as mutually exclusive and all possible control measures should be optimized during farming, transport, slaughtering and processing; to minimize the probability of human disease as much as possible. In fact, complete eradication at farm level and/or complete removal of carcass contamination at the slaughterhouses, are difficult to achieve. Combined interventions covering the whole farm-to-fork chain, are usually considered as the most realistic and effective (FAO, 2001; Havelaar et al., 2007; Dogan et al., 2019; EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011; Nastasijevic et al., 2020; Khalid et al., 2020).

Accordingly, different control measures could be adapted along the food chain (Nastasijevic et al., 2020), depending on the resources available and field applicability. For example, in the specific case of Denmark, the categorization of farms-flocks at higher risk of infection, by using data from the previous year/s (Foddai et al., 2022a), could avoid the need of testing just before logistic slaughter, all the flocks

slaughtered in the country. Moreover, if needed, eventual risk-based mitigation measures could be prioritized during summer at the farm and/or at the slaughterhouse, when flock prevalence and cross-contamination are known to increase significantly (Foddai et al., 2022b) and when approximately one third of the slaughtered flocks, are delivered by “high risk farms”. These represent most of (> 50%) the annual conventional positive flocks (Foddai et al., 2022a). In this way, the costs of eventual additional control measures would be minimized to specific “risky” farms, flocks and time periods. Consequently, the efficiency of such measures, on the risk mitigation, could be optimized.

4.2. Added value of integrating inter-sectorial surveillance data into the risk assessment process

In previous risk assessments (FAO, 2001; Christensen et al., 2001; FAO/WHO, 2009), it was suggested that data describing actual cross-contamination, between originally positive and negative flocks, was needed. Such an issue was addressed in this study. Here, there was no need for simulating the meat contamination level, by assumptions on the relationship between the concentrations of *Campylobacter* spp. in the broiler's gastrointestinal tract and in the skin, which could have caused additional uncertainty around the assessed risk (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011; Nauta et al., 2016, 2022). Most often, the frequency and/or the meat contamination levels of CC flocks need to be simulated, due to lack of data on cross-contamination patterns occurring along the slaughter line (Christensen et al., 2001; Rosenquist et al., 2003; Havelaar et al., 2007; FAO/WHO, 2009). For instance, in Rosenquist et al. (2003), simulations were carried out by using as input, the flock prevalence revealed from pooled faecal samples (Danish data 1998–1999) and the information on carcass contamination from literature. Such data formed the basis for setting the distributions used to model changes in the number of *Campylobacter* present on carcasses, through the slaughtering/processing steps.

In our study, the integration of the surveillance data collected from two different surveillance components (AL and FS), allowed estimating the monthly frequency (AP) of CC and Non-CC flocks (Figs. 2 and 3), and the respective meat contamination distributions for each flock type (Fig. 1a-b). Therefore, firstly, flocks that were more likely to be infected at the farm (carcass positive Non-CC flocks) could be distinguished with good approximation, from those that (instead) could have been contaminated during transport, or in the slaughter plant (CC flocks). Secondly, the monthly contamination levels and the AP could be compared, between the two subpopulations of carcass positive flocks.

As reported previously (Foddai et al., 2022b), CC flocks had lower meat concentrations (log₁₀ cfu/g) of *Campylobacter* than Non-CC flocks (Fig. 1a-b). Those could have very high contamination, even above the limit of 1000 cfu/g (or > 3.0 log₁₀ cfu/g). Thus, if the main target of National Action Plans was to avoid meat contaminations above such a cut-off, then risk-based control measures could be prioritized at the farm level, to reduce the prevalence of Non-CC flocks, which arrive highly positive to the slaughterhouse and can cross-contaminate others.

Moreover, cross-contamination was more likely to occur during summer than in other months (Figs. 2 and 3) (Foddai et al., 2022b). This seasonal pattern is also related to the overall increase of prevalence of positive flocks. It is well known that in Denmark (as in other Northern European countries), the prevalence of infected flocks and the incidence of human cases increase during summer (Wedderkopp et al., 2000, 2001; Patrick et al., 2004; Kuhn et al., 2020; Foddai et al., 2022b).

Next, the simulation model, which represented the risk for the public health sector, could be informed by both the seasonal frequency of flock contamination at different sources (farm vs. transport-slaughter) as well as for the different meat contaminations. Within the model, the risk per serving (Fig. 4) related more to the AP of carcass positive flocks (Figs. 2 and 3), than to the concentration found on contaminated meat (Fig. 1b). The variance in risk (between months) was predominantly driven by the variance in prevalence and less by the variance in cfu/g. This is in

agreement with what is usually found in risk assessments (FAO, 2001; Christensen et al., 2001; Nauta and Havelaar, 2008; Nauta et al., 2009). Accordingly, the risk estimates (Fig. 4), reflected the importance and the monthly variability of both kind of inputs (Figs. 1a, b, 2 and 3). Such a variability should be taken into account when surveillance data and risk assessments are used to inform National Action Plans.

For that reason, the risk per serving was estimated on monthly bases (Fig. 4), considering the CC flocks as carcass negative (scenario II) or as positive (baseline scenario and scenario I), so that their relative importance could be quantitatively assessed (Section 3.3) and could be compared with outputs of other similar studies. For example, in Rosenquist et al. (2003), it was simulated that the increase in the incidence of human campylobacteriosis due to (between-flocks) cross-contamination, could be up to ≈16% (a factor of 1.16). It was concluded that logistic slaughter should have a rather limited effect on the number of human cases (e.g. compared to the introduction of procedures aimed to reduce the concentration of *Campylobacter* on the chickens). Similar conclusions were reached in the study by Nauta et al. (2009), which compared six risk assessment models from different countries. In our study, it was also found that, if cross-contamination had not occurred, the annual level RR of 2018 would have reduced from 0.92 to 0.77 (i.e. by ≈16%). However, there was large monthly variability in the occurrence of the CC flocks (Figs. 2 and 3), which affected their impact on the monthly risk per serving (Fig. 4). Such an effect did not seem irrelevant, especially during summer (Fig. 4), and could be considered to prioritize risk-based control at least during that period of the year.

4.3. Limitations of the study

For 50 out of 999 flocks (5.0%) tested in both surveillance components (AL and FS), it was not possible integrating the datasets on the combination of: farm-ID, house unit and sampling date (Foddai et al., 2022b). Improving the formatting and typing of flock-IDs across components, would increase precision. The unmatched 9 carcass positive flocks, which were classified within the Non-CC category (together with the 152 flocks matched between datasets and positive in both components, Table 1), could not be classified as cross-contaminated. If in reality, those 9 flocks were actually CC flocks, then the risk posed by the latter, could have been slightly underestimated.

Effects of cross-contamination on human health could have been slightly underestimated also because, the cloacal testing of the AL component, could partly overestimate the “true prevalence” of infected flocks (due to test specificity lower than 100%), while the leg-skin testing of the FS component could underestimate the “true prevalence” of carcass positive flocks (due to test sensitivity <100%) (Lund et al., 2004; Rosenquist et al., 2007; Foddai et al., 2022b). Therefore, some of the flocks could have been misclassified as Non-CC (rather than CC) because they appeared positive in both components, but were not infected in reality at the farm level (i.e. were false positive in the AL component and only cross-contaminated on carcasses in reality). Furthermore, some other flocks that were negative in both components could have been actually negative at the farm, but cross-contaminated on carcasses at undetectable levels for the culture test (i.e. correctly classified as negative at the AL component, but false negative in the FS component). Unfortunately, we cannot say exactly if, and in which flocks, the (eventual) testing errors could have occurred, and thus, we could not correct for such an issue at the specific flock level. Nevertheless, the occurrence of such combinations should have been rare and in any case, the risk assessment model was informed with the apparent carcass prevalence in all three scenarios, as is usually the case within the Danish Action Plan. Accordingly, the main conclusions of the study, about the relative contribution of the CC flocks, on the overall risk of human disease, should not have been affected. The classification of flocks into CC and Non-CC appeared realistic in Foddai et al. (2022b), where the statistical analysis showed that the level of meat

contamination was significantly higher in the *Non-CC* flocks. Here as well, the procedure followed to identify the *CC* flocks, appeared representative and precise enough, because for those flocks, the monthly median log₁₀ cfu/g and the monthly frequency of occurrence (apart from May and November) were remarkably lower than these observed in the *Non-CC* flocks (Sections 3.1–3.2). This fits well with the information from literature (Allen et al., 2007; Johannessen et al., 2007; Elvers et al., 2011; Seliwiorstow et al., 2016) and with the logic that, between-flocks cross-contamination is a spill over of *Campylobacter* from originally positive flocks, towards others that arrive at the slaughterhouse as negative.

Moreover, it should be noted that, approximately one third of the conventional flocks tested in the AL component were followed up in the FS component. If all flocks were tested in both surveillance streams, the uncertainty on the interpretation of outputs could be reduced. For instance, in May and November, most of the carcass positive flocks were classified as *CC*. Since this is a retrospective study, we cannot say with 100% confidence, if e.g. in May, i) the six *CC* flocks were caused by the slaughtering of the other two *Non-CC* flocks tested in both components (Fig. 2), or if, ii) they were contaminated from other cloacal positive flocks, which were not followed up in the leg skin testing. Neither we can say if between the non-followed up flocks, there were other *CC* flocks. In that month, a total of 30 flocks were found positive in the AL component (Foddai et al., 2022a) and 8 were positive in the FS component (6 *CC* and 2 *Non-CC*, Fig. 2). Thus, conclusions of this study were based only on the flocks tested in both components and some uncertainty persists, when simulation outputs need to be generalized to all conventional flocks slaughtered in the country. On the other hand, the flocks to be tested in the FS component were chosen randomly at the slaughterhouse and a 33% coverage could be sufficiently representative, to understand the main epidemiological trends of carcass contamination (i.e. at least for most of the investigated flocks and months).

Regarding the size of the tested flocks, it was not available in the data. Only one leg skin sample was taken from each culture tested flock and values below 10 cfu/g were fed as “0” in the model. Hence, variability of carcass contamination, between broilers of the same infected flock, as well as the potential impact of low carcass contaminations on the estimated risk, were not included in the modelling process. However those limitations applied to both flock types (*CC* and *Non-CC*) and within the Danish Action Plan, cfu/g values <10 are considered as posing a very low-negligible risk (Christensen et al., 2013), i.e. are considered as completely negative. Accordingly, the risk assessment focused on the flocks (*CC* and *Non-CC*), which carried some detectable contamination levels (≥ 10 cfu/g). In that context, the aim of the study was to evaluate the “relative” contribution of the *CC* flocks to the risk of human disease, compared to the hypothetical situation where carcass flock positivity due to cross-contamination had not occurred at all.

Finally, it should be kept in mind that in this study, the public health sector and the risk of human campylobacteriosis were represented through the simulation model. Obviously, as for any simulation model, there is some level of error due to the assumptions made during its development and/or due to the lack of data needed to represent some of the simulated variables. For example, the simulation model includes a consumer phase model based on one Dutch study on bacterial transfer and survival during preparation of a chicken salad (Nauta et al., 2008), which was found to perform similarly (but not identically) to other consumer phase models (Nauta and Christensen, 2011); and is not necessarily representative of all poultry meat preparations in Denmark. Also, new dose-response models have been proposed (Teunis et al., 2018), and thus, the uncertainty about these parts of the risk assessment should be kept into consideration (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2020; Nauta et al., 2022). Still, we chose to use the simulation model that has been frequently applied in Denmark, also because in this way we can compare our results with those obtained previously, through the estimation of the RR value. Therefore, although some simplifications had to be used and the final risk estimates cannot be perfect, still the relative importance of

the *CC* flocks on the risk of human disease posed by a serving containing Danish broiler meat, should have been evaluated with good objectivity and approximation (at least for most of the investigated months, e.g. 10/12).

5. Conclusion

This study provided a quantitative assessment of the impact of cross-contaminated (*CC*) flocks on the risk of human campylobacteriosis due to fresh conventional poultry meat produced and consumed in Denmark. The process of data integration and analysis across the animal and food safety components, allowed informing the risk assessment model in a quite repeatable and objective manner along the food chain. Variability of outputs across surveillance months was also taken into consideration. As expected, the risk per serving posed by the *CC* flocks was lower than that posed by *Non-CC* flocks, which arrive at slaughter as positive and remain highly contaminated after processing. However, the risk posed by the *CC* flocks was not negligible, especially during summer, when both the general meat contamination levels and the apparent prevalence increased. We estimated that approximately 16% of the public health risk associated with the consumption of broiler meat is attributable to carcasses obtained from cross-contaminated flocks, while the remaining part is due to the *Non-CC* flocks. This is more than the impact of *CC* flocks estimated in previous quantitative microbiological risk assessments models for broiler chicken processing. Reducing the number of positive flocks entering the slaughterhouse is just as relevant as reducing the *Campylobacter* burden in contaminated flocks and would reduce cross-contamination during transport and slaughter. Both objectives need to be addressed in *Campylobacter* control plans, to mitigate the risk of human disease.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alessandro Foddai: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Maarten Nauta:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Johanne Ellis-Iversen:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

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References

- Allen, V.M., Bull, S.A., Corry, J.E.L., Domingue, G., Jørgensen, F., Frost, J.A., Whyte, R., Gonzalez, A., Elviss, N., Humphrey, T.J., 2007. *Campylobacter* spp. contamination of chicken carcasses during processing in relation to flock colonisation. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 113, 54–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2006.07.011>.
- Anonymous, 2019. Annual Report on Zoonoses in Denmark 2018. National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, pp. 1–61. Available at: <https://www.food.dtu.dk/english/publications/disease-causing-microorganisms/zoonosis-annual-reports>. Accessed on 19/January/2023.
- Berndtson, E., Danielsson-Tham, M.-L., Engvall, A., 1996. *Campylobacter* incidence on a chicken farm and the spread of *Campylobacter* during the slaughter process. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 32, 35–47. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1605\(96\)01102-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1605(96)01102-6).

- Bogaardt M.-J., Mangen M.-J.J., de Wit G.A., Nauta M.J., Havelaar A.H., 2004. Controlling *Campylobacter* in the chicken meat chain. Towards a decision support model. RIVM report 250911005/2004; 1–56. Available at: <https://www.rivm.nl/bibliotheek/rapporten/250911005.html>. Accessed on 05/February/2023.
- Bouwknegt, M., Knol, A.B., van der Sluijs, J.P., Evers, E.G., 2014. Uncertainty of population risk estimates for pathogens based on QMRA or epidemiology: a case study of *Campylobacter* in the Netherlands. Risk Anal. 34, 847–864. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.12153>.
- Boysen, L., Nauta, M., Duarte, A.S.R., Rosenquist, H., 2013. Human risk from thermotolerant *Campylobacter* on broiler meat in Denmark. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 162, 129–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2013.01.009>.
- Christensen, B., Sommer, H., Rosenquist, H., Nielsen, N., 2001. Risk Assessment on *Campylobacter jejuni* in Chicken Products, 1st Edition. The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, Institute of Food Safety and Toxicology, Division of Microbiological Safety, pp. 1–138.
- Christensen, B.B., Nauta, M., Korsgaard, H., Sørensen, A.I.V., Rosenquist, H., Boysen, L., Perge, A., Nørnung, B., 2013. Case-by-case risk assessment of broiler meat batches: an effective control strategy for *Campylobacter*. Food Control 31, 485–490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2012.10.025>.
- Dogan, O.B., Clarke, J., Mattos, F., Wang, B., 2019. A quantitative microbial risk assessment model of *Campylobacter* in broiler chickens: evaluating processing interventions. Food Control 100, 97–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2019.01.003>.
- EFSA and ECDC, 2016. The European Union summary report on trends and sources of zoonoses, zoonotic agents and food-borne outbreaks in 2015. EFSA J. 14, 4634. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2016.4634>.
- EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2011. Scientific opinion on *Campylobacter* in broiler meat production: control options and performance objectives and/or targets at different stages of the food chain. EFSA J. 9, 1–141. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2105>.
- EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2020. EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards (BIOHAZ) Koutsoumanis, K., Allende, A., Alvarez-Ordóñez, A., Bolton, D., Bover-Cid, S., Davies, R., De Cesare, A., Herman, L., Hilbert, F., Lindqvist, R., Nauta, M., Peixe, L., Ru, G., Simmons, M., Skandamis, P., Suffredini, E., Alter, T., Crotta, M., Ellis-Iversen, J., Hempen, M., Messens, W., Chemaly, M., 2020. Update and review of control options for *Campylobacter* in broilers at primary production. EFSA J., 18, 1–89. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6090.
- Elvers, K.T., Morris, V.K., Newell, D.G., Allen, V.M., 2011. Molecular tracking, through processing, of *Campylobacter* strains colonizing broiler flocks. Appl. Environ. Microb. 77, 5722–5729. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02419-10>.
- Evers, E.G., Bouwknegt, M., 2016. Combining QMRA and epidemiology to estimate campylobacteriosis incidence. Risk Anal. 36, 1959–1968. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.12538>.
- FAO [Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations], 2001. Risk assessment of thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp. in broiler chickens. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/3/y8145e/y8145e07.htm>. Accessed on 07/02/2023.
- FAO/WHO [Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations/World Health Organization], 2009. Risk assessment of *Campylobacter* spp. in broiler chickens: Technical Report. Microbiological Risk Assessment Series No 12. Geneva.132pp. Available at: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/43731>. Accessed on 06/February/2023.
- Foddai, A., Nauta, M., Ellis-Iversen, J., 2022a. Risk-based control of *Campylobacter* spp. in broiler farms and slaughtered flocks to mitigate risk of human campylobacteriosis – a one health approach. Microb. Risk Anal. 21 (100190), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2021.100190>.
- Foddai, A., Takeuchi-Storm, N., Hög, B.B., Kjeldgaard, J.S., Andersen, J.K., Ellis-Iversen, J., 2022b. Assessing *Campylobacter* cross-contamination of Danish broiler flocks at slaughterhouses considering true flock prevalence estimates and ad-hoc sampling. Microb. Risk Anal. 21 (100214), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2022.100214>.
- Food Safety Commission of Japan, 2009. Risk Assessment of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* in Poultry. Evaluation Report of Microorganisms and Viruses. Food Safety Commission of Japan, 25 June (in Japanese).
- Gantzhorn, M.R., Pires, S.M., Ellis-Iversen, J., Kuhn, K., Nielsen, E.M., 2018. Status on *Campylobacter* in Denmark. Anonymous, 2018. Annual report on Zoonoses in Denmark 2017. National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, pp. 15–21. Available at: www.food.dtu.dk/english/publications/disease-causing-microorganisms/zoonosis-annual-reports. Accessed on 03/October/2022.
- Habib, I., Berkvens, D., De Zutter, L., Dierick, K., Van Huffel, X., Speybroeck, N., Geeraerd, A.H., Uyttendaele, M., 2012. *Campylobacter* contamination in broiler carcasses and correlation with slaughterhouses operational hygiene inspection. Food Microbiol. 29, 105–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2011.09.004>.
- Hansson, I., Sandberg, M., Habib, I., Lowman, R., Engvall, E.O., 2018. Knowledge gaps in control of *Campylobacter* for prevention of campylobacteriosis. Transbound. Emerg. Dis. 65, 30–48. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.12870>.
- Havelaar, A.H., Mangen, M.-J.J., de Koeijer, A.A., Bogaardt, M.-J., Evers, E.G., Jakobs-Reitsma, W.F., van Pelt, W., Wagenaar, J.A., de Wit, G.A., van der Zee, H., Nauta, M. J., 2007. Effectiveness and efficiency of controlling *Campylobacter* on broiler chicken meat. Special issue on *Campylobacter* risk management and assessment (CARMA). Risk Anal. 27, 831–844. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2007.00926.x>.
- Havelaar, A.H., Ivarsson, S., Löfdahl, M., Nauta, M.J., 2013. Estimating the true incidence of campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis in the European Union, 2009. Epidemiol. Infect. 141, 293–302. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950268812000568>.
- Houe, H., Nielsen, S.S., Nielsen, L.R., Ethelberg, S., Mølbak, K., 2019. Opportunities for improved disease surveillance and control by use of integrated data on animal and human health. Front. Vet. Sci. 6, 301. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00301>.
- Johannessen, G.S., Johnsen, G., Økland, M., Cudjoe, K.S., Hofshagen, M., 2007. Enumeration of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. from poultry carcasses at the end of the slaughter-line. Lett. Appl. Microbiol. 44, 92–97. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-765X.2006.02026.x>.
- Khalid, T., Hdaifeh, A., Federighi, M., Cummins, E., Boué, G., Guillou, S., Tesson, V., 2020. Review of quantitative microbial risk assessment in poultry meat: the central position of consumer behaviour. Foods 9, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9111661>.
- Kuhn, K.G., Nygård, K.M., Guzman-Herrador, B., Sunde, L.S., Rimhanen-Finne, R., Trönnberg, L., Jepsen, M.R., Ruuhela, R., Wong, W.K., Ethelberg, S., 2020. *Campylobacter* infections expected to increase due to climate change in Northern Europe. Sci. Rep. 10, 13874. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-70593-y>.
- Lund, M., Nordentoft, S., Pedersen, K., Madsen, M., 2004. Detection of *Campylobacter* spp. in chicken fecal samples by real-time PCR. J. Clin. Microbiol. 42, 5125–5132. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.42.11.5125-5132.2004>.
- Mangen, M.-J.J., Havelaar, A.H., Poppe, K.J., 2005. Controlling *Campylobacter* in the chicken meat chain. Estimation of Intervention Costs. Agricultural Economics Research Institute (LEI), The Hague, pp. 1–70. Project code 20223. April 2005. Report 6.05.01. ISBN 90-5242-990-1.
- Miwa, N., Takegahara, Y., Terai, K., Kato, H., Takeuchi, T., 2003. *Campylobacter jejuni* contamination on broiler carcasses of C. jejuni-negative flocks during processing in a Japanese slaughterhouse. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 84, 105–109. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(02\)00398-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(02)00398-7).
- Nastasićević, I., Proscia, F., Boskovic, M., Glisic, M., Blagojevic, B., Sorgentone, S., Kirbis, A., Ferri, M., 2020. The European Union control strategy for *Campylobacter* spp. in the broiler meat chain. J. Food Saf. 40, e12819. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfs.12819>.
- Nauta, M., Christensen, B., 2011. The impact of consumer phase models in microbial risk analysis. Risk Anal. 31, 255–265. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2010.01481.x>.
- Nauta, M.J., Havelaar, A.H., 2008. Risk-based standards for *Campylobacter* in the broiler meat chain. Food Control 19, 372–381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2007.04.016>.
- Nauta, M.J., Fischer, A.R.H., van Asselt, E.D., de Jong, A.E.I., Frewer, L.J., de Jonge, R., 2008. Food safety in the domestic environment: the effect of consumer risk information on human disease risks. Risk Anal. 28, 179–192. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1539-6924.2008.01012.x>.
- Nauta, M., Hill, A., Rosenquist, H., Brynstad, S., Fetsch, A., van der Logt, P., Fazil, A., Christensen, B., Katsma, E., Borck, B., Havelaar, A., 2009. A comparison of risk assessments on *Campylobacter* in broiler meat. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 129, 107–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2008.12.001>.
- Nauta, M.J., Sanaa, M., Havelaar, A.H., 2012. Risk based microbiological criteria for *Campylobacter* in broiler meat in the European Union. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 158, 209–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2012.07.018>.
- Nauta, M.J., Johannessen, G., Adame, L.L., Williams, N., Rosenquist, H., 2016. The effect of reducing numbers of *Campylobacter* in broiler intestines on human health risk. Microb. Risk Anal. (2–3), 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2016.02.001>.
- Nauta, M., Bolton, D., Crotta, M., Ellis-Iversen, J., Alter, T., Hempen, M., Messens, W., Chemaly, M., 2022. An updated assessment of the effect of control options to reduce *Campylobacter* concentrations in broiler caeca on human health risk in the European Union. Microb. Risk Anal. 21, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2021.100197>.
- Nordic Committee on Food Analysis, 2007. Thermotolerant *Campylobacter*. Detection, Semi-Quantitative and Quantitative Determination in Foods and Drinking Water. Nordic Committee on Food Analysis (NMKL, 119, 3.Ed., 2007).
- Osiriphun, S., Iamtaweejaloen, P., Kooprasertying, P., Koetsinchai, W., Tuitemwong, K., Erickson, L.E., Tuitemwong, P., 2011. Exposure assessment and process sensitivity analysis of the contamination of *Campylobacter* in poultry products. Poult. Sci. 90, 1562–1573. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2009-00577>.
- Patrick, M.E., Christiansen, L.E., Waino, M., Ethelberg, S., Madsen, H., Wegener, H.C., 2004. Effects of climate on incidence of *Campylobacter* spp. in humans and prevalence in broiler flocks in Denmark. Appl. Environ. Microb. 70, 7474–7480. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.70.12.7474-7480.2004>.
- Pires, S.M., Jakobsen, L.S., Ellis-Iversen, J., Pessoa, J., Ethelberg, S., 2020. Burden of disease estimates of seven pathogens commonly transmitted through foods in Denmark, 2017. Foodborne Pathog. Dis. 17, 322–339. <https://doi.org/10.1089/fpd.2019.2705>.
- R Core Team, 2013. R: a language and environment for statistical computing and graphics. The R project for statistical computing. <http://www.R-project.org/>.
- Rasschaert, G., De Zutter, L., Herman, L., Heyndrickx, M., 2020. *Campylobacter* contamination of broilers: the role of transport and slaughterhouse. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 322, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2020.108564>.
- Rosenquist, H., Nielsen, N.L., Sommer, H.M., Nørnung, B., Christensen, B.B., 2003. Quantitative risk assessment of human campylobacteriosis associated with thermophilic *Campylobacter* species in chickens. Int. J. Food Microb. 83, 87–103. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(02\)00317-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(02)00317-3).
- Rosenquist, H., Sommer, H.M., Nielsen, N.L., Christensen, B.B., 2006. The effect of slaughter operations on the contamination of chicken carcasses with thermotolerant *Campylobacter*. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 108, 226–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2005.12.007>.
- Rosenquist, H., Bengtsson, A., Hansen, T.B., 2007. A collaborative study on a Nordic standard protocol for detection and enumeration of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in food (NMKL 119, 3. Ed., 2007). Int. J. Food Microbiol. 118, 201–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2007.07.037>.
- Sasaki, Y., Maruyama, N., Zou, B., Haruna, M., Kusukawa, M., Murakami, M., Asai, T., Tsujiyama, Y., Yamada, Y., 2013. *Campylobacter* cross-contamination of chicken

- products at an abattoir. *Zoonoses Public Health* 60, 134–140. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1863-2378.2012.01509.x>.
- Seliwiorstow, T., Baré, J., Van Damme, I., Algaba, I.G., Uyttendaele, M., De Zutter, L., 2016. Transfer of *Campylobacter* from a positive batch to broiler carcasses of a subsequently slaughtered negative batch: a quantitative approach. *J. Food Protect.* 79, 896–901. <https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028X.JFP-15-486>.
- Teunis, P.F.M., Havelaar, A.H., 2000. The beta poisson dose-response model is not a single-hit model. *Risk Anal.* 20, 513–520. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0272-4332.204048>.
- Teunis, P.F.M., Bonacić Marinović, A., Tribble, D.R., Porter, C.K., Swart, A., 2018. Acute illness from *Campylobacter jejuni* may require high doses while infection occurs at low doses. *Epidemics* 24, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epidem.2018.02.001>.
- Wedderkopp, A., Rattenborg, E., Madsen, M., 2000. National surveillance of *Campylobacter* in broilers at slaughter in Denmark in 1998. *Avian Dis.* 44, 993–999.
- Wedderkopp, A., Gradel, K.O., Jørgensen, J.C., Madsen, M., 2001. Pre-harvest surveillance of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* in Danish broiler flocks: a 2-year study. *Int. J. Food Microb.* 68, 53–59. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0168-1605\(01\)00463-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0168-1605(01)00463-9).
- WHO, 2020. *Campylobacter*. WHO. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/campylobacter#>.
- Zhang, X., Tang, M., Zhou, Q., Zhang, J., Yang, X., Gao, Y., 2018. Prevalence and characteristics of *Campylobacter* throughout the slaughter process of different broiler batches. *Front. Microbiol.* 9, 2092 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.02092>.
- Zhao, G., Huang, X., Zhao, J., Liu, N., Li, Y., Wang, L., Gao, Y., Wang, J., Qu, Z., Liu, J., Wang, J., 2020. Risk prevention and control points through quantitative evaluation of *Campylobacter* in a large broiler slaughterhouse. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 7, 172 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.00172>.